

Flend Your Class for Better Student Engagement

Khalid Fethi (May 2023)

Abstract:- The FLEND methodology, an instructional design model that stands for Flip and Blend (integrated), has been developed through deep reflection on the fast-paced changes occurring in the world today. With intense competition in technology, artificial intelligence, business, medicine, and other fields, it is crucial for education to equip young learners with a diverse range of prerequisite skills that enable them to adapt to the demands of the 21st century. As Franklin D. Roosevelt said, 'We cannot always build the future for our youth, but we can build our youth for the future.' The core concept of FLEND is to provide a flexible and engaging learning experience in a digital-based class, enabling learners to explore, understand, analyze, evaluate, and assimilate content more quickly. Equally important, FLEND aims to develop highly essential skills, often referred to as the 5Cs: communication, collaboration, critical thinking, creativity, and citizenship. These skills are invaluable and cannot be challenged by AI.

I. INTRODUCTION

As an English educator, my primary goal is to facilitate the shift from knowledge-based teaching to skill and value-based learning, with a focus on cultivating a collaborative mindset among our classes. To support this, we integrate online and in-person classes to offer a more holistic student-centered approach. Our overriding objective is to develop students' English language proficiency while simultaneously honing their soft skills, social and emotional intelligence, and instilling essential human values within a digital-based learning environment. In this paper, we will address the following questions: What is the difference between Flipped and blended learning? How does FLEND integrate both methodologies? What are the FLEND stages, processes, features, and rationales? How do we integrate critical thinking with creativity? How do we transition from words to videos through the poster stage? Why and when do we invite experts to interact? How does the e-meet session help students assess their learning outcomes?

Table 1: FIIP – BLEND – FLEND: Description

Flipped Learning	Blended Learning	FLEND
Flipped Learning is a pedagogical approach in which direct instruction moves from the group learning space to the individual learning space, and the resulting group space is transformed into a dynamic, interactive learning environment where the educator guides students as they apply concepts and engage creatively in the subject matter. (Bergmann & Sams, 2014)	Blended Learning is an approach to learning that combines face-to-face and online learning experiences. Ideally, each (both online and offline) will complement the other by using its particular strength. Context: While generally seen as a 'trend' in 'progressive learning,' Blended Learning can also be viewed as a kind of relic symbolic of the gap between 'traditional education' (for the last century or so in brick-and-mortar schools and classrooms) and connected and digital learning. This implies that digital-only is the future and the ultimate incarnation of learning, which is a short-sighted view. The point, though, is that blended learning is a mix of old and new as much as it is a mix of physical and digital learning. (Staff, 2022)	FLEND is based on combining the Flip and Blend approaches, which I consider to be harmonious and complementary. It provides students with a flexible, engaging, and group-oriented learning experience. In other words, throughout the different stages of the lesson, the teachers will adopt alternately two methodologies: a- Flipped Learning for: - OCA (Out of Class Activities), - ICA (In Class Activities), also called group space activities. b- Blended Learning for: - asynchronous production - Creativity activities.

II. FLEND DIFFERENT STAGES, PROCESSES, FEATURES, AND RATIONALE

The FLEND methodology comprises four stages, each with a specific process, distinguishing features, and definite rationale.

A. Stage 1: Prelude

Table 2: Flend Different Stages, Processes, Features, And Rationale

Activities	Process	Features	Rationale
A- Creative Fluency	The students examine a picture, a set of pictures, or a short video before being asked to generate as many ideas as possible in a very limited amount of time. Then, they	1- The picture(s) or the video should be relevant to the lesson theme. 2- The time set for the activity should be 3 to 5 minutes, depending on the student's	This is a visual intelligence activity aimed at: 1- Broadening students' imagination to help develop their problem-solving skills.

	share their ideas with their classmates, either in pairs or groups.	ability to express themselves. 3- The picture(s) can include useful vocabulary. 4- During the sharing time, students can freely move in class from one group to another	2- Developing students' communication and fluency. 3- Encouraging students to use their vocabulary to express themselves coherently. 4- Developing self-esteem and a sense of belonging. 5- Having fun while learning.
B- Title Finding	On the basis of the details, the students guess the lesson title	The teacher, with the students, creates a mind map that collects the main words that describe the picture or video. Then, they come up with a title that covers and connects the description.	This activity, which starts with a mind map, accomplishes several objectives: 1- It helps the students develop meaningful learning (Allrich, n.d.). 2- It implicitly teaches conciseness. 3- It helps the teacher gather more feedback and observe the students' reactions to different interventions. 4- It serves as the first stage to boost conceptual thinking (Marschall, 2019), which the students will later apply in critical thinking exercises. 5- It is fun and highly engaging.
C- Theme Exploration	The teacher assigns a quiz activity to assess the student's knowledge about the theme (Sample)	The 5-minute quiz introduces the subject in an interactive and engaging way. The students, in pairs or groups, complete the different multiple-choice-based questions, and they are allowed to see the answers at the end before receiving feedback.	This interactive activity helps students explore the cultural context of the theme, broadening their perspective and promoting understanding and empathy, particularly when dealing with sensitive issues such as poverty and homelessness. Equally important, it helps develop in-class communication and collaboration. Unlike lecturing, the activity encourages students to be independent, search for information, and learn while sharing in a friendly atmosphere. The feedback is typically fast because student engagement in the activity helps with the quick assimilation of content.
D- F2FF	This stands for Face to Face Fluency	In pairs, the students share what they learned from the quiz and the feedback. The time limit is 2-3 minutes.	Apart from the fun time, the students develop their speaking fluency while sharing the information they have got, in a very limited amount of time.

E- Data Bank	The students, in groups, use Padlet, to conduct some intensive research and share as much information as possible about the target subject. The data bank can be used in the coming activities including speaking and writing.	This mini-project activity lasts for 10 minutes. The students use different websites, including the Chat GPT website, to select information relevant to the subject. Afterward, they move to a sharing session where they analyze and evaluate their research outcomes in new groups. They have the freedom to edit their posts by deleting or adding information as needed.	This activity helps the students develop: a- Independent reading b- Some reading strategies: scanning, skimming, selecting, and making connections c- Asking the right questions d- Drawing conclusions from the different passages. e- Communication, teamwork, and critical thinking.
F-Mind Map	The teacher prepares the template and shares it with the students for completion. The mind map should include some questions that guide the students.	The Mind Map activity takes 7-10 minutes. In groups, they complete their task by answering the different questions and preparing for the Mini-Presentation.	This activity has plenty of benefits that complement the preceding one: a- Selection b- Organization c- Memory retention d- Communication
F- Quote Bank	This activity is planned only for intermediate and advanced students. They are asked to select a quote relevant to the subject and use Canva to create their poster and share it on a Padlet link. (Sample)	As this is the first stage of digital creativity, the students should find the appropriate poster that describes the selected quote. They not only post their created poster but also need to comment on others' posts.	This highly interactive activity is designed to achieve the following objectives: 1- Develop students' language skills through the use of quotes, facilitating their learning and improving concise writing. 2- Foster creativity from an early stage. 3- Enhance online interaction by leveraging the commenting feature on Padlet, allowing students to provide feedback on each other's posts. 4- Promote the practice of Netiquette (What Is Netiquette? 20 Rules Internet Etiquette Rules, 2023) for socializing, having fun, and maintaining proper online etiquette. 5- Create a database of information that students will utilize in future lesson stages.
G- Poster creating	On the basis of the different quotes, the students, in groups, select one and create a poster that describes the quote in an artistic way	The students, in groups, complete a 10-minute poster-creating activity. Then, they present and discuss the content as well as the artistic feature of their project.	The main goals of this activity are: 1- Understanding and assimilating the selected quote that reflects the lesson message. 2- Developing the student's creativity, including digital ones. 3- Honing the social and emotional learning (SEL), as the students, in a supportive

			environment, develop active listening, constructive feedback, and self-esteem and confidence.
H- My English in Use.	This is a writing/speaking activity based on the students' outcomes from the different preceding activities. In other words, they turn their first mind map, title, and quote into a paragraph. After writing, the students orally share their deductions.	We call it 'Raw English in Use' because, at this stage, the teacher does not teach new vocabulary to the students. It serves as a pre-pre-teaching vocabulary stage where the teacher implicitly assesses the students' reactions to a new topic, solely relying on their existing personal vocabulary.	This activity will help the students: 1- try their own way to express themselves coherently, relying on their personal vocabulary. 2- turn the notes taken into a structured paragraph that includes the selected quote. 3- assess their progress, identify their strength, and point out their weakness. 4- Develop peer-to-peer learning (Edith Cowan University, Perth, Western Australia, 2016), as they will listen and learn from their partners.

The prelude is considered the first pillar of the FLEND class. It not only introduces the new topic but also helps the students assess and measure their ongoing progress through four major activities:

- creative fluency,
- title finding,
- information selection and mind mapping,
- quote poster creating and sharing,
- and ultimately writing using only English words that have been developed before the pre-teaching vocabulary.

Equally important, this stage lays the foundation for forthcoming targeted soft and leadership skills, including critical and creativity, collaboration, and communication. We also start honing digital creativity skills as early as possible.

B. Stage 2: Flip: OCA

Before introducing the different Out of Class Activities (OCA), we need to answer the following question: What are the features of the OCA compared to the homework?

Table 3: Different Out of Class Activities (OCA)

Homework	Out-of-Class Activities / Individual Space Learning
The students practice what they have learned in class	1. The students explore a new lesson.
It is frustrating because some students, for different reasons, could not have assimilated the content in class	2. It is motivating because a variety of well-structured questions will guide the students toward content assimilation.
It is mostly paper-based	3. It is digital-based.
It can be long and tedious	4. It should be concise and interactive.
It targets knowledge construction (A, 2009b)	5. It targets knowledge construction and skill development.
The students worry about failing or showing their flaws and weaknesses	6. It is stress-free, as the students know that it is not an assignment.
When it comes to in-class feedback, the best students make a difference in class while the average or struggling ones will be more frustrated and even excluded.	7. The whole class is highly motivated to share their answers before receiving feedback and practicing.

The OCA (Out-of-Class Activity) is not a homework assignment or a form of formative assessment (A, 2009b), nor is it equivalent to Blended Learning, which involves the combination of in-class or face-to-face education with online learning (Solutions, 2022). In Flipped Learning, the

OCA is a set of instructed activities that are digitally based, short, engaging, and interactive. These activities are designed for students to explore, understand, and assimilate the lesson content while implicitly developing their cognitive and non-cognitive skills.

Table 4: OCA: Stages and features:

Stages	Features	Rationale
Gift Time	This activity is planned to complement the main subject: song, funny or culture-based video...	This activity Introduces the OCA lesson in an entertaining and informative way.
Vocabulary	This is a pre-teaching vocabulary activity. It introduces the keywords, expressions, and idioms that the students will find in the comprehension. We generally use some apps, such as Quizziz or WordWall.	This interactive activity helps the students explore and develop their vocabulary.
Comprehension	The comprehension stage includes listening and/or reading, depending on the length and importance of the material. Edpuzzle app is used for listening comprehension while Teacher Made is used to assign comprehension activities. As mentioned earlier, the questions prepared in these activities should be short, varied, and structured in a way that helps the students find the answer rather than assessing their understanding.	This activity will help the students develop their listening and reading skills. Equally important, the activity process will motivate the students to develop a passion for reading and listening comprehension.
Summary	This activity is part of the communication part. The students are requested to connect the different answers to come up with a summary paragraph.	This activity is a self-assessment task that helps the students develop their writing skills along with reflecting on their ability to deal with listening/reading comprehension, which remains one of the biggest challenges the students face. Equally important, the students understand that a very good summary will pave the way for better engagement in the forthcoming in-class activities.
Smart question (Smart Q.)	The students prepare 2 questions that they will ask in class.	This activity helps the students develop their critical thinking skills. It fuels their curiosity and also helps the teachers assess their understanding (Asking Effective Questions - Chicago Center for Teaching and Learning, n.d.)

III. FLIP: ICA

After completing the OCA, the students have a variety of In class activities (ICA) that target both cognitive and non-cognitive skills. The first stage is called [SHAC](#) (Khalid & Helaine, 2017) protocol. This stands for Share – Help – Ask – Comment. This is a peer collaboration activity whose main global goals are:

- Active participation
- Deeper peer learning
- Collective intelligence
- Higher motivation
- Socialization
- Communication
- Collaboration
- Critical thinking
- Digital Learning

The table below describes the different activities and their rationale.

Table 5: Different activities and their rationale.

Time Frame	Activity	Description	Rationale
7 minutes, repeated twice.	Share and Help	In small groups, the students are requested to share what they have learned from the OCA. It is a café talk-like activity, as the students should informally share every single detail possible about what and how they have answered the different assigned questions. They freely give their opinions on the lessons they have learned and the different challenges they have faced.	This activity helps the students develop the following skills: a- Spontaneous interaction b- Collaboration, as the students share everything they have: c- Peer Listening d- Speaking Fluency e- Note-taking This activity also boosts the students' self-confidence and motivates them to socialize and speak openly and without hesitation.
5 minutes, repeated three times	Ask and Comment	This is a group then pair work activity. The students ask the questions they have prepared in the OCA, listen to their peers, and comment on the answers. Most of the best questions are selected for a separate activity called: Smart Q.	As mentioned earlier, this stage paves the way for developing the student's critical thinking skills.

The teacher's role is limited to monitoring and taking note of common mistakes that require urgent correction, which is often related to word choice and word order errors. Students are requested to move from one pre-determined class station to another and take notes using an organized note-taking system (such as the [Cornell note-taking method](#)), digital apps, or shorthand. Along with the goals stated above, students develop their note-taking skills, including information selection, note review, and revision, reflection, active listening, and in-class engagement.

The major challenge we notice during SHAC time is how to integrate students who have missed their OCA (Out of Class Activities) into the in-class interactive learning process. Students who complete their OCAs are highly motivated to share their ideas and discuss different perspectives related to the lesson content. They enjoy active engagement in various activities. On the other hand, students who haven't completed their OCAs tend to be passive recipients of information. Their disruptive and sometimes irrelevant questions can hinder interaction and become a burden in the classroom. Consequently, since SHAC time is a crucial component and its effectiveness is a top priority, teachers should clearly communicate the importance of completing OCAs seriously and before the deadline. The effectiveness of SHAC time greatly depends on the completion of OCAs.

After the SHAC time, students participate in a six-minute activity called F2FF, which stands for face-to-face fluency. In pairs, they retell, refine, and reflect (3Rs) on the OCA. This peer-feedback stage helps students communicate in English with ease, accuracy, and confidence. In other words, students try to convey their learning outcomes and ideas clearly and efficiently. Equally important, the fluency activity improves students' cognitive development, especially memory and critical thinking. Moreover, students

learn how to connect what they are reading to their own [background knowledge](#) (Hoffman, 2021).

The Smart Question Com. is the third in-class activity that students complete before the OCA global feedback. After selecting and refining the best questions suggested by students in their OCA, teachers plan writing and then speaking activities with the following goals:

- Accuracy: Students select appropriate words and organize their ideas to convey a message accurately.
- Effective communication: After writing, editing, and revising their paragraphs, students can confidently, eloquently, and fluently communicate their thoughts.
- Critical thinking: Students share, analyze, and evaluate different answers.
- Creative fluency: Students generate as many suggestions as possible in a limited amount of time.
- Art of persuasion: Students try to communicate convincingly using data and real-life stories to persuade classmates.
- Collective intelligence: Students contribute their ideas in a friendly and active environment.
- Use of technology: Teachers allow students to use their digital devices to conduct instant research and support their premises more persuasively.

IV. BLEND: ONLINE PRODUCTION ACTIVITY

After the face-to-face in-class or online activities that have included SHAC time, fluency, and smart Q., the teacher assigns an online asynchronous production activity that fosters the student's assimilation and evaluates their understanding of the material covered in the lessons. I usually use [Padlet app](#), an easy-to-use virtual collaborative space, where the students share their essays and comment on their peers' posts. This activity allows the class to develop the following skills:

- Writing
- Thinking critically and creatively
- Sharing, discussing and even debating
- Peer learning and peer-feedback
- Developing self-confidence
- Social interaction
- Digital skill building

Equally important, this online formative assessment tool helps the teachers track the students' progress, provide timely [descriptive feedback](#) (*Types of Feedback*, 2022), appreciate their efforts, adjust the instruction, prepare for the coming in-class feedback, and recommend resources, in an interactive digital environment.

A. IN-CLASS FEEDBACK:

➤ Language

In a FLEND class, the teachers should ensure that the online and in-class language feedback complements each other throughout the different stages. While the former is mostly brief, directive (Staff, 2022), and appreciative, the latter should be corrective.

After examining and evaluating the different OCA language answers, the first day ICA, and the online production activity, the teacher gains a global idea of the different mistakes that should be addressed urgently and meticulously. They can adopt an elaborated corrective feedback (ECF) approach (Corrective Feedback | WingInstitute.org, n.d.) along with the test-teach-test (TTT) method. In a collaborative environment, the students use their digital devices to complete the different tasks, each followed by ECF.

To complete an interactive task based on pre-selected errors, the teacher assigns the first quiz using tools such as Quizizz. Here are some practical guidelines:

- Relevant to the lesson objectives
- Easy, accurate, and concise
- Varied question types
- Balanced difficulty
- Timed appropriately
- Engaging visuals
- Mobile-friendly
- Concise feedback

After completing the assigned quiz, the teacher moves to the second "T," which is teaching. As we aim for interactive, collaborative classes that promote active engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students, teachers should elicit answers. In other words, they should draw out responses or any information from students through questioning instead of lecturing or providing direct information.

The third "T" stands for Test. The teacher assigns two more in-class, digitally-based tasks: practice-oriented and production-oriented activities, in order to ensure that students have assimilated the lesson outcome. Here are some practical tips:

- Different apps
- Relevance
- Clarity and accuracy
- Challenging questions
- Variety of materials including visuals.
- Feedback incorporation after each question and at the end of the activity
- Time limit
- Leaderboard for motivation

B. In-class feedback:

➤ Comprehension

The OCA comprehension assessment is not intended to measure students' understanding of a particular material, whether it be a passage, video, or audio. Therefore, the questions are designed to facilitate comprehension and guide students to the correct answers. They are direct, clear, and concise. If the teacher presents a video or audio, they will often repeat important information. The passage should not be long and should include a limited number of difficult words that have already been dealt with in the pre-teaching vocabulary task. Additionally, the questions are prepared in a way that helps students connect the answers and formulate a summary, which they can use during the SHAC time.

The feedback on the OCA comprehension prepares students for the digital-based jigsaw reading activity, which they complete in groups called stations. The teacher provides the students with a pre-designed mind map to guide their work. This intensive reading task will help the students develop the following skills:

- Collaborative Learning (Collaborative Learning | Center for Teaching Innovation, n.d.): The students develop higher-level thinking, oral communication, and leadership skills.
- Social connection: The students develop their social skills (Magazine, 2022), including how to lead a team effectively, confidence, listening, non-verbal communication, eye contact, body language, and self-control.
- Active participation: The students actively engage with the selected passage, ask questions, and discuss their thoughts with their team. This will undoubtedly develop their critical thinking.
- Enhanced understanding: The students gain a deeper understanding of the passage by listening to different interpretations and insights.
- Critical reading: The students use various resources to prepare persuasive arguments, and in doing so, they sometimes unintentionally practice critical reading techniques such as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of the given information (Linda, 1989).
- Note making: The students transition from note-taking to note-making. This skill "is more than just writing down what you read or hear; it is also a process of synthesizing and revisiting concepts from... reading" (*Styles of Note Making: Note Making Format, Procedure, and Advantages*, 2022).

After completing the group reading, making notes, and turning them into a mind map, the teacher creates new groups with students from different stations. Each student is then asked to explain their assigned article using only their digital mind map. This activity fosters the skills listed above and helps the students learn more from their peers, and develop their cognitive and non-cognitive skills in a friendly and enjoyable environment.

➤ *Blend: Online production activity*

Using Padlet platform, the students turn the in-class input into out-of-class output, by answering the teacher’s open-ended question. They write their essay that shows the retained information, presents their reflection on what they read, noted, and learned from their peers, and demonstrates

how they structure the different ideas and insights concisely, coherently, and accurately. lastly, it prepares them for the coming stage: Creativity.

➤ *FLEND: Creativity:*

Creativity is the ultimate and most important stage in our FLEND (Flip-Blend) classes. A successful lesson is evaluated based on the student’s engagement and achievements. In other words, creativity activities, which take three classes, provide teachers with an opportunity to assess their students’ cognitive and non-cognitive skills in a fair, practical, and stress-free way. Some of the activities and stages are listed below along with their processes and rationales:

Table 6: Activities and stages with their processes and rationales

Stage	Project	Description	Rationale
One	Presentation.	<p>Depending on the theme and the skills the teacher intends to work on, he assigns one of these:</p> <p>a- <u>Oral presentation</u>: the students work in groups on a five minute a problem-solving project related to the completed lesson. They use Canva app, as an example, to create visual aids to accompany their oral presentation and adopt the SMART goals strategy to explain, elaborate and convince their classmates.</p> <p>b- <u>Pecha-Kucha style</u> (<i>What Is a Pecha Kucha Presentation?</i>, n.d.) : the students work in groups on a theme-based project. They, very concisely and accurately state the problem and the viable solutions. Then, the team speaker presents the 20-slide project in 6 minutes and 40 seconds.</p> <p>c- <u>Motivational speech</u>: This is an individual task. Each student is expected to present his 1-2-minute talk to address an issue discussed along the unit. He has to provide practical solutions.</p> <p>d- <u>In-class debate</u>: The students in groups, opponent vs proponents, are requested to create their network, share their arguments on Padlet, read their opponents’ counterarguments, and then we move to the team debate.</p> <p>e- <u>Poster presentation</u>: the students, in groups, create digital posters that summarize, creatively, the lesson goals. They discuss their projects with their peers and visitors, including parents.</p>	<p>Communication skills: while presenting, the students develop their listening (they learn how to become active listeners) and speaking skills (they work on fluency, articulation, and eloquence) along with the art of presenting their ideas and insights in an organized and coherent way.</p> <p>Sharing the workload: The students collaboratively share the different tasks before and while presenting. This will reduce stress and help to build confidence. As each student strives to complete their assigned tasks can ensure that each person’s strengths are utilized. This will lead to a well-rounded final product.</p> <p>Engagement: we can witness two types of engagement:</p> <p>a- The group engagement: the students can be highly engaged while preparing their presentation</p> <p>b- Class engagement: having different speakers, with different voices, insights, and arguments, help the students get more motivated to actively listen and give their feedback.</p> <p>Creative and critical thinking: The students generate a lot of ideas, and even compete to come up with different perspectives, on the subject they are presenting. In addition to this, they evaluate the credibility and relevance of the data and inspire each other to come up with impressive solutions.</p>
Two	Video Making	The best presentations are turned into videos that the school leader shares on	Motivation and networking: The students get more motivated when they see their work is seen and appreciated

		social media.	<p>by others. Additionally, it helps them with networking opportunities.</p> <p>Feedback: By posting their work online, students can receive valuable feedback and some suggestions from a wider audience, including peers. This can help them improve some speaking skills, body language, pronunciation, tone, pace and fluency. Equally important, they will care more about perfecting the quality of their work, both in terms of the content and technical aspects, like video audio quality.</p>
Three	Elite Meet	<p>After completing their projects and assimilating the lesson content very well, the students meet with an expert, such as an author, researcher or scholar, who work on the same theme. The meeting allows the students to learn from the expert's perspective and knowledge.</p>	<p>Inspiration and motivation: Meeting with experts can be inspiring and motivating for students. Experts can share their personal experiences and success stories, which can encourage students to work harder and pursue their goals with great determination and enthusiasm.</p> <p>Networking: meeting with experts allow the students to build interesting relationships with individuals, who can offer them guidance and assistance.</p> <p>Insights and Feedback: The students can learn from the expert's knowledge and personal experience. Hence, they reconsider their choices and address their flaws. They can also enhance their critical thinking by asking more questions to deepen their understanding.</p>
four	E-journal	<p>The students create and complete their e-journal throughout the unit, in which they save their lessons, essays, posters, projects, and videos. I recommend that the teachers use the Canva app, which is free and easy to use.</p>	<p>Digital skills: the use of the e-journal help the students develop their IT skills and get more engaged in the digital world.</p> <p>Organization: the students learn how to organize appropriately their work to make both lesson tracking and activities access easier.</p> <p>Reflection and feedback: The e-journal will help the students, their peers, and teachers check it out and give their opinions or offer feedback easily.</p> <p>Creativity: Creating and completing the e-journal helps the students develop their creativity: they learn how to choose the appropriate background, colors, effects, animation, and so on.</p>

V. CONCLUSION

The FLEND (Flip – Blend integration) methodology aims to create a flexible learning experience that bridges in-class and out-of-class learning environments into a single space where the virtual and face to face worlds converge: What begins in class can be continued outside of it. Students in both spaces are connected and can communicate, collaborate, and create together. While doing this, they promote a lot of essential skills, including leadership, SEL and digital. It is worth-noting that the FLEND methodology proves that the skills cannot be developed separately. They are inextricably intertwined: We cannot, for instance, develop collective intelligence without efficient communication, effective critical thinking, and smart use of technology.

The FLEND methodology considers creativity a top priority and encourages students to engage in creative activities throughout the different stages of the learning process. During the Prelude stage, students create digital posters summarizing the lesson concept. In the Production stage, after comprehension and feedback activities, students write essays and articles. In the Creativity stage, students are required to give different types of presentations, including oral presentations, Pecha Kucha, posters, video making, and e-journal creating.

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Appendix:

- [21.] Artificial Intelligence. Sample quiz. <https://shorturl.at/sxJRY>
- [22.] Discipline, quote bank. Padlet: <https://shorturl.at/dGU38>
- [23.] Take Note: Popular Study Method has 'Cornell' Written All Over It. Retrieved from: <https://alumni.cornell.edu/cornellians/cornell-notes/>
- [24.] <https://padlet.com/>